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Abstracts

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FunGlass

Improvement of corrosion behavior of aluminium and magnesium alloys by graphene based hybrid silica sol-gel coatings

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Abstract

The discovery of graphene in 2004 as a single layer of SP² hybridized carbon atoms with superior physical, chemical, mechanical and electrical properties has triggered considerable theoretical and experimental studies for industrial applications such as polymer-composites, energy-related materials, sensors, field-effect transistors and biomedical applications[1-3] Graphene nanosheets and graphene oxide have the potential to improve the tribological and anti-corrosion properties when it integrated with other ceramic or polymeric materials as nanofiller [4-6].

In this study, graphene nanosheets were incorporated into hybrid silica sols to prepare silica coatings as promising candidate to replace the chromate conversion coatings. The silica sols were prepared using Tetraethoxysilane (TEOS) and 3-glycidoxypropyl-trimethoxysilane (GPTMS) as precursors of silica with the addition of graphene nanosheets (GNs) with the average flake size of 1-3 micrometer. The hydrolysis and condensation reactions together with the opening of epoxy rings were studied by UV-vis-NIR spectroscopy and ATR-FTIR. The effect of incorporating GNs in the synthesis of silica sols was also investigated. Moreover, hybrid silica sol-gel coatings were prepared by dip-coating using the silica sols with and without GNs on Al₂₀₂₄-T3 and anodized AZ31B substrates. According to preliminary results, graphene based coatings showed more compact structure, smoother surface and slightly higher contact angle compared to silica coatings without GNs. Coatings based on GNs improved the corrosion behavior of the metal alloys compared to coatings without GNs.

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